

ROLE OF GENDER INFLUENCE AND CONSUMER ATTITUDE IN DIGITAL ADVERTISING

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Abstract:

Gender is considered one of the top segmentation factors that the targeting of the advertising towards shopping message is based on. Consumer attitudes are a composite of a consumer's (1) beliefs about, (2) feelings about, (3) and behavioural intentions toward some object--within the context of marketing, usually a brand or retail store. These components are viewed together since they are highly interdependent and together represent forces that influence how the consumer will react to the object. This research aims at investigating the attitude of customers towards digital advertising towards shopping in Coimbatore city. The study will be based on primary data with survey method and the data will be collected from 100 respondents who are surfing internet actively.

Key Words: Gender, Consumer Attitudes and Retail Store

Introduction:

Consumers' differences according to gender have always been an interest to marketers so having known the differences between males and females regarding their beliefs about and attitudes towards advertising towards shopping, will allow marketers to spend money on advertising towards shopping in more targeted way. That is, many studies that have investigated the differences between males and females, have revealed the existence of significant differences in beliefs about and attitudes towards advertising towards shopping that were explained by gender. Those results are consistent with what have reached, that males differ from females in processing the promotional information delivered by advertising towards shopping.

The importance of gender as a market segmentation variable lies on the fact that gender is one of the few variables that meet the criteria required for an easily successful application of market segmentation. Those criteria are:

- Identifiability;
- Accessibility: especially for the internet, that facilitates approaching gender classes so easily.
- Profitability: gender classes are big enough to make profits.

With a variable meeting the above mentioned criteria, gender is considered a main variable that can be used in marketing analysis for many variables including advertising towards shopping effectiveness which represented with consumers' attitudes towards advertising towards shopping.

Along the way to defining gender, and though the existence of masculinity and femininity levels, it does not necessarily make sense to evaluate gender as a continuous variable, because research in this field have indicated that results would be the same whether gender is operationalised as a binary construct or as a continuous construct. Consequently, advertisers should recognize and understand the gendered patterns regarding beliefs about and attitudes towards advertising towards shopping, so advertisers can use those gendered patterns to produce "gender-specific" advertisements has found that advertising towards shopping directed to just males or just females is more effective than advertising towards shopping directed to both males and females. Though some authors have found no differences between males and females regarding few factors (e.g. time spent on digital social networks), differences are, however, present between males and females regarding many factors within the internet context. Examples of these differences:

- Females use the internet less than males do.
- Goals behind using the internet are different between males and females. Males use the internet for purposes related to entertainment and leisure. While females are more interested in using the internet for interpersonal communication and educational assistance (Weiser, 2000);
- Males and females are different in making purchase decisions;
- Females indicate a strong dislike for not being able to savour a physically fulfilling shopping experience digital.
- Males have more positive beliefs and attitudes towards digital advertising towards shopping.

All the above mentioned examples support the importance of differences between males and females in the marketing process, and consequently in the targeting process within the industry of digital advertising towards shopping.

Beliefs about Digital Advertising towards Shopping:

In general, beliefs are typically conceptualized as estimates of the likelihood that the knowledge one has acquired about a referent is correct or, alternatively, that an event or state of affairs has or will occur.

Consequently, a belief about digital advertising towards shopping is all knowledge that perceived to be correct for digital advertising towards shopping.

The importance of beliefs about advertising towards shopping lies in the previous research findings that beliefs are predictors of attitudes towards advertising towards shopping. The role of gender in beliefs about advertising towards shopping has been investigated in several studies. It have found that males report more favourable beliefs about advertising towards shopping in general, and this finding is valid for digital advertising towards shopping as have indicated. The most common dimensions of beliefs about advertising towards shopping are as follows:

- Information: as advertising towards shopping provides consumers with product-related information.
- Entertainment: digital advertising towards shopping could offer the availability of interactivity and multimedia, so it could be perceived by consumers as a source of pleasure and entertainment.
- Social role: as a form of mass media communication, digital advertising towards shopping can be used for promoting specific lifestyles through the advertised brands and products.
- Irritation: digital advertising towards shopping could be annoying. For example consumers might perceive digital advertising towards shopping as an insult to their intelligence, or even abusive. Also digital advertising towards shopping could be confusing to consumers when they are exposed to large amounts of advertising towards shopping message.
- Materialism: when consumption is viewed as a way for people to achieve satisfaction.
- Falsity: like other forms of advertising towards shopping, digital advertising towards shopping sometimes do not tell the truth in their claims about products advertised, therefore falls into the trap of giving deceptive claims.
- Values corruption: digital advertising towards shopping has the ability to shape internet users' value, therefore digital advertising towards shopping has the chance to corrupt those values.

Statement of the Problem:

According to consumers, internet advertising towards shopping includes many forms of commercial content from electronic advertisements that are similar to traditional advertisements (e.g., billboards, banner ads) to formats that are different from traditional advertisements, such as corporate Web site. The problem is to know about the impact of advertising towards shopping towards gender in Coimbatore region.

Objectives of the Study:

- To study about concepts involved in customer perception.
- To study about the beliefs, feelings and behavioral intentions of customers.
- To analyze the attitude of customers based on factors information, entertainment, social role, falsity and value corruption.
- To suggest about the perception of customers about digital advertising towards shopping.

Scope of the Study:

The study is about analysing the impact of gender in digital advertising towards shopping. The main scope of the study is that it will be helped for the companies to know about the customer's attitude and influence of gender towards digital advertising towards shopping. In future the study may be extended to include the impact of advertising towards shopping in improving the customer retention.

Research Methodology:

Source of Data:

The type of data collected comprises of primary and secondary data.

- Primary data: The primary data is the first hand data collected from the employees through questionnaire. The questionnaire is a structured one. It is made simple and avoids misunderstanding to the respondents.
- Secondary data: The secondary data has been collected from the reports and official publications of the organization, journals, statutory welfare schemes from websites, some reviews said by employees, collection of circulars between the customers of digital advertising towards shopping about the awareness based on gender.

Sampling Method:

Sampling method refers to the rules and procedures by which some elements of the population are included in the sample. Some common method is simple random sampling, stratified sampling, cluster sampling etc... it mainly depends on survey objectives and survey resources. In this research simple random sampling is used, in statistics it is a subset of individuals (a sample) chosen from a larger set (a population). Each individual is chosen randomly and entirely by chance, such that each individual has the same probability of being chosen at any stage during the sampling process and each subset of individuals has the same probability of being chosen for sample as any other subset of individuals this process and techniques is known as simple random sampling.

Sample Design:

The study is based primary data collected on sample survey technique. It consists of customer awareness about digital advertising towards shopping based on gender. Sample of 100 were selected and their views and opinions are collected on different parameters. Personal interviews and informal discussions were held with the employees as well.

Tools & Techniques:

Simple percentage, Chi square analysis and Ranking method

Limitation of Study:

- The study is confined only to the Coimbatore city hence it cannot be considered as a representation of entire area.
- Availability of information and data are limited by time factor.
- The number of respondents is limited to only 100, and the opinion may differ from person to person.

Analysis and Interpretation:

Table 1: Demographic Variables of the Respondents

Demographic Variables	Particulars	Frequency	Percent
Age	Below 25	40	40
	25 to 35 years	12	12
	36 to 45 years	40	40
	Above 45 years	8	8
	Total	100	100
Gender	Male	66	66
	Female	34	34
	Total	100	100
Educational qualification	SSLC	16	16
	Diploma	17	17
	HSC	32	32
	Degree holders	35	35
	Total	100	100

The above table shows that 40% are of the age group of below 25 yrs, 12% are in the age group of 25 to 35 yrs, 40% are in the age group of 36 to 45 yrs, and 8% are in the age group of above 45yrs. 66% and female of 34% in the survey. 16% of them have completed SSLC, 17% of them has completed diploma, 32% of them has completed HSC, and 35% of them has completed degree.

Preference of Like towards Digital Advertisement towards Shopping Digital:

	Number of Respondents	Percentage
Like it very much	41	41
Like it	15	15
Neutral	10	10
I do not like it	20	20
I do not like it all	14	14
Total	100	100

The above table shows the preference of like towards digital advertisement towards shopping digital by the respondents were 41% of them like very much, 15% of them like it, 10% of them are neutral, 20% of them don't like it and 14% of them don't like it all.

Frequency of Watching Digital Advertisements for the Products:

	Number of Respondents	Percentage
1 Times	19	19
2 Times	33	33
3 Times	48	48
Total	100	100

The above table shows about advertisements for the products that 19% of them have seen the advertisements 1 time, 33% has seen the advertisements 2 times, 48% of them has seen the advertisements 3 times.

Understanding Advertisements:

	Number of Respondents	Percentage
No	22	22
A little	34	34
Yes	44	44
Total	100	100

The above table shows that 22% are not understanding advertisements, 34% are understanding a little, 44% are understanding and they are not confused about the advertisement.

Level of Acceptance towards Advertising Factors:

	SA		A		N		D		SD	
	NO	%								
Acceptance on product in pop up	6	6	9	9	12	12	22	22	51	51
Acceptance on using gender for advertisement	32	32	41	41	4	4	8	8	15	15
Acceptance on models with a improper dress code	42	42	15	15	10	10	19	19	14	14
Acceptance on using different models to promote each and every product of their company	44	44	31	31	6	6	13	13	6	6
Acceptance on effective traditional media	20	20	31	31	18	18	10	10	21	21
Acceptance on neglecting an advertisement in mobile	32	32	38	38	6	6	14	14	10	10
Acceptance on intention of females to buy digital is less than that of males	44	44	22	22	14	14	15	15	5	5
Acceptance on significant gap	21	21	22	22	6	6	44	44	7	7

From the above table 6% of the respondents strongly agree for acceptance on product in pop up, 32% of the respondents strongly agree for acceptance on using gender for advertisement, 42% of the respondents strongly agree for using models with a improper dress code, 44% of the respondents strongly agree for acceptance on using different models to promote each and every product of their company, 20% of the respondents strongly agree on effective traditional media, 32% of the respondents strongly agree for acceptance on neglecting an advertisement in mobile, 44% of the respondents strongly agree for acceptance on intention of females to buy digital is less than that of males and 21% of the respondents strongly agree for acceptance significant gender gap in consumers.

9% of the respondents strongly agree for acceptance on product in pop up, 41% of the respondents strongly agree for acceptance on using gender for advertisement, 15% of the respondents strongly agree for using models with a improper dress code, 31% of the respondents strongly agree for acceptance on using different models to promote each and every product of their company, 31% of the respondents strongly agree on effective traditional media, 38% of the respondents strongly agree for acceptance on neglecting an advertisement in mobile, 22% of the respondents strongly agree for acceptance on intention of females to buy digital is less than that of males and 22% of the respondents strongly agree for acceptance significant gender gap in consumers.

12% of the respondents neutral for acceptance on product in pop up, 4% of the respondents neutral for acceptance on using gender for advertisement, 10% of the respondents neutral for using models with a improper dress code, 13% of the respondents neutral for acceptance on using different models to promote each and every product of their company, 18% of the respondents neutral on effective traditional media, 6% of the respondents neutral for acceptance on neglecting an advertisement in mobile, 14% of the respondents neutral for acceptance on intention of females to buy digital is less than that of males and 6% of the respondents neutral for acceptance significant gender gap in consumers.

6% of the respondents neutral for acceptance on product in pop up, 32% of the respondents neutral for acceptance on using gender for advertisement, 42% of the respondents neutral for using models with a improper dress code, 44% of the respondents neutral for acceptance on using different models to promote each and every product of their company, 20% of the respondents neutral on effective traditional media, 32% of the respondents neutral for acceptance on neglecting an advertisement in mobile, 44% of the respondents neutral for acceptance on intention of females to buy digital is less than that of males and 21% of the respondents neutral for acceptance significant gender gap in consumers.

22% of the respondents disagree for acceptance on product in pop up, 8% of the respondents disagree for acceptance on using gender for advertisement, 19% of the respondents disagree for using models with a improper dress code, 13% of the respondents disagree for acceptance on using different models to promote each and every product of their company, 10% of the respondents disagree on effective traditional media, 14% of the respondents disagree for acceptance on neglecting an advertisement in mobile, 15% of the respondents disagree for acceptance on intention of females to buy digital is less than that of males and 44% of the respondents disagree for acceptance significant gender gap in consumers.

51% of the respondents disagree for acceptance on product in pop up, 15% of the respondents strongly

disagree for acceptance on using gender for advertisement, 19% of the respondents strongly disagree for using models with a improper dress code, 21% of the respondents strongly disagree for acceptance on using different models to promote each and every product of their company, 10% of the respondents strongly disagree on effective traditional media, 10% of the respondents strongly disagree for acceptance on neglecting an advertisement in mobile, 5% of the respondents strongly disagree for acceptance on intention of females to buy digital is less than that of males and 44% of the respondents strongly disagree for acceptance significant gender gap in consumers.

Chi Square:

Comparison between Age and Watching Digital Advertisements for the Products:

H0: There is no significant relationship between age and watching digital advertisements for the products

Age * Watching digital advertisements for the products					
Count		Watching digital advertisements for the products			Total
		1 times	2 times	3 times	
Age	Below 25	11	10	19	40
	25 to 35 years	2	5	5	12
	36 to 45 years	6	16	18	40
	Above 45 years	0	2	6	8
Total		19	33	48	100

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	6.603 ^a	6	0.359

The above table shows about the chi square analysis (at 5% significance level) reveals that there is no significance between these factors as the calculated value is less than table value at 6 degree of freedom.

Rank Analysis:

Factors	Rank						
	1	2	3	4	5		
Influences customer by a negative review	23	28	33	8	8	250	2
Consumer perceive higher level of risk	23	50	13	6	8	226	5
Switch over of brand because of models used	42	14	7	31	6	245	3
Marketing channel has a largest combination for brand promotion based on gender	6	3	27	37	0	241	4
Information given by the advertising towards shopping is informative	6	14	17	28	35	372	1

The above table shows about the rank analysis of watching digital advertisements. Were information given by the advertising towards shopping is informative was given first rank, Influences customer by a negative review was given second rank, Switch over of brand because of models used was given third rank, Marketing channel has a largest combination for brand promotion based on gender was given fourth rank and Consumer perceive higher level of risk was given fifth rank which shows that Information given by the advertising towards shopping is informative was given first priority by the respondents.

Findings:

- Maximum of the respondents are from the age group of below 25 and in our survey.
- Most of the respondents are male in our survey.
- Maximum of the respondents have completed degree in our survey.
- Most of the respondents like digital advertisement very much.
- Most of the respondents have seen the digital advertisement for the products 3 times in our survey.
- Maximum of the respondents strongly disagree for acceptance on product in pop up.
- Most of the respondents agree for acceptance on using gender for advertisement.
- Maximum of the respondents strongly agree for using models with a improper dress code
- most of the respondents strongly disagree for acceptance on using different models to promote each and every product of their company
- Maximum of the respondents agree for acceptance on effective traditional media
- Most of the respondents strongly agree for acceptance on neglecting an advertisement in mobile
- Maximum of the respondents strongly agree for acceptance on intention of females to buy digital is less than that of males
- Most of the respondents strongly disagree for acceptance significant gender gap in consumers
- Maximum of the respondents are using blogs and forums are using gender a lot for advertising towards shopping

Suggestions:

- Most of the respondents like digital advertisement very much and they accept that advertising towards shopping in digital are an effective traditional media shows that more advertisement about the products can be given in digital so that the product can be used among customers.
- The respondents strongly disagree for acceptance on using different models to promote each and every product of their company and it shows that the models are not having impact on the brand and new innovative concepts can be created so that more advertisements can be published as per customer's requirements.

Conclusion:

The conclusion is that most of the respondents like digital advertisement very much and they accept that advertising towards shopping in digital is an effective traditional media shows that more advertisement about the products can be given in digital so that the product can be used among customers. The respondents strongly disagree for acceptance on using different models to promote each and every product of their company and it shows that the models are not having impact on the brand and new innovative concepts can be created so that more advertisements can be published as per customer's requirements.

References:

1. Alwitt, L. F., & Prabhakar, P. R (1992). Functional and Belief Dimensions of Attitudes to Television Advertising. *Journal of Advertising towards shopping Research*, 32(5), 30-42.
2. Alwitt, L. F. & Prabhakar, P. R (1994). Identifying who dislikes television advertising towards shopping: Not by demographics alone. *Journal of Advertising towards shopping Research*, 34 (6), 17–29.
3. Andrews, J. C. (1989). The Dimensionality of Beliefs towards Advertising towards shopping in General. *Journal of Advertising*, 18(1), 26 –35.
4. Andrews, W. (1997). On Wall Street's IPO Short List: Point Cast and Marimba. *Web Week*, 3(8), 34 – 36.
5. Bank, D.(1996). How the Net Is Becoming More Like Television to Draw Advertisers. *Wall Street Journal*, A1.
6. Bauer R. A., & Greyser, S. A. (1968). Advertising towards shopping in America: The Consumer View. Boston: Harvard University, Graduate School of Business Administration, Division of Research.
7. Berthon, P., Pitt, L. F., & Watson, R. T. (1996). The World Wide Web as Advertising towards shopping Medium: Toward an Understanding of Conversion Efficiency. *Journal of Advertising towards shopping Research*, 43–54.
8. Briggs, R. & Hollis, N. (1997). Advertising towards shopping on the Web: Is There Response before Click-Through? *Journal of Advertising towards shopping Research*, 37, 33– 45.
9. Consumer Reports (1997). Guarding Young Web-Surf- ers: Don't Count on Special Software to Protect Kid's Privacy, 17.